

Dyes Derived from 4,5-Dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic Acid. Part I. Effect of Introducing Methyl Groups and also of Decreasing Unsaturation in the Phthalic Acid Portion of Phthalein Dyes

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4,5-Dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic acid in the form of its anhydride has been condensed with a number of aromatic hydroxy (phenols) and hydroxyamino (*m*-diethylaminophenol) compounds. The phthalein and rhodamine type of compounds, thus obtained, have been studied analytically and spectrophotometrically and also these have been compared with similar compounds obtained from phthalic acid. The resorcinol compound has also been brominated and acetylated. The effect of introducing methyl groups and also of decreasing unsaturation in the phthalic acid portion of phthaleins have been studied.

4,5-Dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (I), prepared from 2,3-dimethylbutadiene and maleic anhydride¹, was condensed with resorcinol, orcinol, phenol, phloroglucinol, pyrogallol, *o*-cresol, and *m*-diethylaminophenol under different conditions. The phthalein and rhodamine type of dyes obtained were purified and analysed. The resorcinol compound was brominated and acetylated. The phthaleins prepared were studied spectrophotometrically and the absorption maxima were compared with those of phthaleins and rhodamines obtained from phthalic anhydride.

The phthaleins and rhodamines obtained are of the following types:

Phthaleins and rhodamines—Type (1).

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|---|---|
| II: R ¹ =R ² =R ⁴ =H; R ³ =OH. | III: R ¹ =Me; R ² =R ⁴ =H; R ³ =OH. |
| IV: R ¹ =R ³ =OH; R ² =R ⁴ =H. | V: R ¹ =R ² =H; R ³ =R ⁴ =OH. |
| VI: R ¹ =R ² =R ⁴ =H; R ³ =NEt ₂ . | VII: R ¹ =H; R ² =R ⁴ =Br; R ³ =OH. |
| VIII: R ¹ =R ² =R ⁴ =H; R ³ =OCOMe. | |

1. Farmer and Warren, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 897.

Phthaleins — Type (2).

IX : R' = OH; R² = H.

X : R' = OH; R² = Me.

EXPERIMENTAL

2,3-Dimethylbutadiene, obtained from pinacol², was condensed with maleic anhydride to yield 4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride¹ (I). The anhydride (I) was crystallised from light petroleum and melted at 78-79°. This was used for the preparation of phthaleins and rhodamines, described below.

Resorcinol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (II).—The anhydride (I) (2 g.) and resorcinol (2.5 g.) were intimately mixed and heated to 160° in an oil bath. A few drops of H₂SO₄ (conc., 3-4) were added and the temperature raised to 180°. The condensation was complete in about 3 hours. The product after cooling was extracted with dilute NaOH solution and filtered. The phthalein was then precipitated by adding HCl (dil.) in small portions to the alkaline filtrate. The crude phthalein was further purified by precipitation method followed by crystallisation from ethanol. The brick-red crystals thus obtained were dried at 110° in an electric oven.

The crystals, m.p. 210° (decomp.), dissolve in ethanol with an orange-green fluorescence which changes to red-green on addition of alkali. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 5.52. C₂₂H₂₀O₅ requires C, 72.5; H, 5.5%).

Orcinol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (III).—An intimate mixture of the anhydride (I) (2 g.) and orcinol (3 g.) was heated to 140-60° for 4 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 3-4 drops). The condensed product was extracted with dilute NaOH solution and filtered. The phthalein was precipitated and purified as above, m.p. 200° (decomp.).

It is a dark red crystalline substance which dissolves in alkalis exhibiting a yellow-green fluorescence. The ethanolic solution is yellow. (Found: C, 73.1; H, 6.16. C₂₄H₂₄O₅ requires C, 73.47; H, 6.12%).

Phloroglucinol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IV).—An intimate mixture of the anhydride (I) (2 g.) and phloroglucinol (2.9 g.) was heated from 180° to 200° for 4 hours

2. Kyriakides, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **36**, 967.

in presence of H_2SO_4 (conc., 3-4 drops) as the condensing agent. The phthalein was extracted, precipitated, and purified as above.

It is a brown-red crystalline substance which dissolves in alkalis giving an orange-red colour. The ethanolic solution is also orange-red, m.p. 245° (blackens and decomposes). (Found: C, 66.1; H, 5.1. $C_{22}H_{20}O_7$ requires C, 66.6; H, 5.05%).

Pyrogallol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (V) was prepared similarly by heating an intimate mixture of the anhydride (I) (2 g.) and pyrogallol (2.9 g.). The product was powdered, washed with distilled water, and extracted with a very dilute NaOH solution. The phthalein was then precipitated and purified as usual.

It is a black crystalline substance, m.p. 230° (decomp.) which dissolves in ethanol giving a yellowish brown solution which changes to red-brown on adding alkali. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 5.2. $C_{22}H_{20}O_7$ requires C, 66.6, H, 5.05%).

m-Diethylaminophenol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (VI) was obtained in a similar way as (V) on heating the anhydride (I) (2 g.) and *m*-diethylaminophenol (3 g.) for about 3 hours. The condensed mass was extracted by HCl (dil.) and filtered. The rhodamine was precipitated by adding dilute NaOH solution to the acidic filtrate. The dye-stuff was further purified by a second precipitation and subsequent crystallisation from ethanol. Finally it was dried at 110° in the electric oven.

It is a pink-coloured crystalline substance, melting above 300° . It dissolves in ethanol with a deep pink colour which is intensified to a purple pink by addition of HCl (dil.). (Found: C, 75.7; H, 8.2; N, 5.89. $C_{30}H_{38}O_5N_2$ requires C, 75.94; H, 8.00; N, 5.90%).

Tetrabromoresorcinol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (VII) was obtained by brominating resorcinol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (II), using the method of Baeyer³.

It is a dark red crystalline powder, melting above 300° . Ethanolic solution is pink which becomes more intense on adding alkali. (Found: Br, 46.6. $C_{22}H_{16}O_5Br_4$ requires Br, 47.0%).

Resorcinol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalcin diacetate (VIII) was obtained by acetylating the resorcinol compound (II) with acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate. It was purified by crystallising from ethanol as a brownish crystalline substance, m.p. 150° (darkens and decomposes). (Found: C, 69.58; H, 5.40. $C_{26}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 69.64; H, 5.36%).

Phenol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IX).—A mixture of the anhydride (I) (2 g.) and an excess of phenol (3.6 g.) was heated at 110° to 115° for about 14 hours in presence of H_2SO_4 (8 drops, conc.). The condensed semisolid mass was poured in water (50 ml) and the excess of phenol was removed by steam distillation. The crude solid residue was extracted with very dilute NaOH and the phthalein precipitated by HCl (dil.). The compound was purified by decolorising with animal charcoal and crystallised from ethanol-water (2:1) mixture.

It is a pinkish white powder, m.p. 180° . The ethanolic solution is yellowish brown, which turns pink on adding alkali. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 6.32. $C_{22}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 75.43; H, 6.28%).

3. *Annalen*, 1878, 183, 3.

o-Cresol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (X).—A mixture of the anhydride (I) (2 g.) and *o*-cresol (4 g.) was heated at 110° to 115° for about 14 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (8 drops, conc.). The phthalein was separated and purified in the same way as (IX).

It is a brown powder, m.p. 200° (decomp.). The ethanolic solution is brown which turns to purple-pink on adding alkali. (Found: C, 75.9; H, 6.9. C₂₄H₂₆O₄ requires C, 76.19; H, 6.87%).

The absorption maxima were determined by using the 'Hilger Uvispek' spectrophotometer. The maxima for the phthalein type of compounds were taken in ethanolic solutions containing a drop of 5% NaOH (Table I) and the maximum for the rhodamine type of compound was taken in ethanolic solution containing a drop of 5*N*-HCl (Table II). The absorption maxima of phthaleins and rhodamines from phthalic acid were also determined under similar conditions, using the same apparatus.

TABLE I

Phenols.	Phthaleins.	4,5-Dimethyl- Δ^4 tetrahydrophthaleins.
Resorcinol	490 m μ (fluorescein)	485 m μ
Orcinol	490 (orcein)	505
Phenol	545 (phenolphthalein)	545
Phloroglucinol	460	465
<i>o</i> -Cresol	560	542
Tetrabromoresorcinol	515 (eosin)	515

TABLE II

(From phthalic anhydride)	(From 4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride)
<i>m</i> -Diethylaminophenol-phthalein (Rhodamine B)	<i>m</i> -Diethylaminophenol-4,5-dimethyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein
545 m μ	540 m μ

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